
THE NUMBER AND TYPE OF NARRATORS IN LITERARY WORK

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Annotation. This article gives information about narration in literary work. Narration or storytelling began with the oral tradition. Myths, legends, fables, ballads, and folktales were performed aloud to entertain and inform an audience. These narratives were memorized using mnemonic devices such as oral-formulaic composition, which utilizes repetition of the same phrases that fit into specific metrical conditions. The canonical spiritual works of world religions—such as Buddhism, Hinduism, Judaism, Islam, and Catholicism—have roots in the oral tradition, as do epic poems like Homer’s Iliad and Odyssey, the Norse Eddas and Sagas, the Mesopotamian Epic of Gilgamesh, and the Anglo-Saxon Beowulf. In this article, we gave information about all types of narrators.

Key words: narrator, first-person narrator, limited, unreliable narrator, the style, multiple narrators.

The word/term, narrator, is derived from the Latin term, *narrator*, which typically means a person who narrates or relates facts, or events, etc. In other words, the narrator could be a historian, an observer, or an active participant in the events. In grammar, it is a noun of narrating. In literary terms, it is a person who tells a story from his or her point of view. Thus, could be several types of narrators in literature. Who is a Narrator? A narrator is a person or voice who tells a story or narrates a literary work. The story or the literary work is described from the narrator's point of view. A narrator can be part of the text. However, it is not mandatory for the narrator in literature to be part of the text. The presence of narrators is found in fictional stories, novels or even narrative poems. The narrator may or may not be present in the events narrated in the literature. The voice of the character can dictate the style and subject matter of the poem, story or book, and the reader can be so close as to actually ‘inhabit’ the character. At other times, the characters are mysterious, kept at a distance, their inner lives unknown³⁸.

The narrator's different perspective on narrating an event or character discloses many facets of the narrative. The readers get some space to think and summarize their conclusion on various parts of the literature. Therefore, the narrator is not only a describer but also a guide. It guides the reader to get the correct knowledge from the

³⁸Maggie Hamand. Creative Writing For Dummies. 2009y John Wiley and Sons, Ltd, Chichester, West Sussex-p.57

literature without getting lost among the characters and the plot. Narrators in literature have an essential purpose to offer. If we can identify different narrators in literature, it will be easier to understand the perspective. Narrators are the backbone of fictional literary works. This tutorial will assist in getting the essential details on narrators in literature³⁹.

In literary works, the narrator is the individual or entity that tells the story to the reader. The number and type of narrators can vary depending on the narrative style and the specific literary work. Here are some common types of narrators:

First-person narrator: This type of narrator is a character in the story who uses the first-person pronoun "I" to recount the events. The story is told from their perspective, and they are often a major character or the protagonist. First-person narrators provide a subjective and personal account of the events, sharing their thoughts, feelings, and experiences. Examples include Holden Caulfield in "The Catcher in the Rye" by J.D. Salinger and Scout Finch in "To Kill a Mockingbird" by Harper Lee.

Third-person limited narrator: This type of narrator is external to the story and uses third-person pronouns ("he," "she," "they") to describe the characters and events. However, the narration is limited to the thoughts and experiences of a single character. The reader sees the story through the eyes of this character, gaining insight into their perspective. This type of narration allows for a deeper understanding of the character's thoughts and emotions. An example is Winston Smith in George Orwell's "1984." **Third-person Limited Narrator:** It narrates everything from the third-person point of view using the pronouns mentioned before. In addition, such a narrator can be the part of the event intruding on the narration. Stories are narrated from a point of view, but occasionally the narrator, of whatever kind, modulates the style of narration to take account of the point of view of some other character⁴⁰.

It can also stay outside of the incidents in the narrative. Such narrators comment on the characters too. The narrator is 'limited' because such a narrator does not have the authority to comment on the characters outside a story's scenes. When this narrator is present around the characters, it can comment on these. Among the most popular series of novels, we must mention Harry Potter's series of J. K Rowling has the 'third-person limited point of view'. For example, Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets shows Harry's thoughts but mainly focuses on the events related to the characters with the third person limited point of view.

Third-person omniscient narrator: This type of narrator is also external to the story but has access to the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of multiple characters.

³⁹ <https://www.tutorialspoint.com/narrators-in-literature-types-and-definitions>

⁴⁰ Gregory Currie. Narratives and Narrators A Philosophy of Stories.- New York: Oxford University Press Inc, 2010.- p.20

They can provide insight into different characters' perspectives, allowing the reader to see the story from various angles. The third-person omniscient narrator has a broader and more objective view of the events. An example is the narrator in Leo Tolstoy's "War and Peace." Third-person Omniscient Narrator: This narrator explains and narrates staying outside the narrative and its events. Such narrators cannot be the part or character of the narrative. It is called a 'third-person omniscient narrator because the narrator acts like knowing everything or being aware of everything that happens.

The narrator's presence is felt everywhere in the text by the readers. And the narrator acts as the omniscient God who knows all. This type of narrator is usual in stories and novels or fictional narratives.

Jane Austen's famous novel *Pride and Prejudice* is an example of the third-person omniscient narrative point of view. The narrator is aware of the incidents and thoughts of the character and acts like an omniscient presence.

Unreliable narrator: An unreliable narrator is a character who tells the story but provides a distorted or skewed version of events due to their limited understanding, personal biases, or deliberate manipulation. The reader may need to question the narrator's credibility and interpret the story with caution. Examples of unreliable narrators can be found in "Lolita" by Vladimir Nabokov and "The Great Gatsby" by F. Scott Fitzgerald. The idea of narrative is of course in some ways at odds with contemporary treatments of the dispersion of the knowing subject, which resist assumptions of the continuity of consciousness implicit in the aspiration to unified stories of the past⁴¹.

Multiple narrators: Some literary works employ multiple narrators who take turns telling the story from their respective perspectives. Each narrator offers their unique viewpoint, and their narratives may intersect or diverge. This narrative technique allows for a multifaceted exploration of the story and its characters. An example is "As I Lay Dying" by William Faulkner, which features multiple narrators from the same family.

These are just a few examples of the different types of narrators in literary works. Authors often employ various narrative techniques to achieve specific effects and engage readers in different ways.

The style of writing, plot perspective, or even characters' attributes depend on the narrators. Narrators in literature have an essential purpose to offer. If we can identify different narrators in literature, it will be easier to understand the perspective. Narrators are the backbone of fictional literary works. This tutorial will assist in getting the essential details on narrators in literature.

⁴¹ Genevieve Lloyd. *Being in Time Selves and narrators in philosophy and literature.* - New York: Routledge, 2005.- p.18.

In the novel by Robin Sharma, 'The Monk Who Sold His Ferrari,' the narrator is John. The whole story is known to the readers mainly by the conversations between John and Julian Mantel, who eventually changed his perspectives about life.

Second-person narrator. The second-person narrator narrates, addressing the reader. It uses the pronoun 'you', 'your' and 'yours' to narrate any fictional story or novel. The second-person narrator is not popular in the literature. The reader becomes confused with the second-person narrator because it does not specify if the reader is getting a part in the narrative. 'Ghost Light' by Joseph O'Connor is a novel that shows the ups and downs of the life of an Irish actress, Maire O'Neill or Molly Allgood. This impactful novel is an incredible example of the second-person narrative. We see the growth and fall of the relationship between the characters John Millington Synge and Molly Allgood through the second-person point of view⁴².

As a conclusion we can say whenever we read a novel, short story, poem, or academic essay, we're looking at a form of narration. The art of storytelling (or academic writing) takes a lot of consideration. Choosing the topic isn't enough. We must also choose how to convey the topic to the reader. In a moment, we'll work through three types of narration: first person, second person, and third person. Each serves its own purpose. As a writer, you can choose to tell a story any way you'd like. This is known as point of view. There are three popular forms: First Person - In this point of view, a character (typically the protagonist, but not always) is telling the story. You'll notice a lot of "I" and "me" or "we" in first person narrations. Second Person - In this point of view, the author uses a narrator to speak to the reader. You'll notice a lot of "you," "your," and "yours" in second person narration. Third Person - In this point of view, an external narrator is telling the story. You'll notice a lot of "he," "she," "it," or "they" in this form of narration.

The list of used literature:

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